

IMPACT OF AGRICULTURAL SCHEMES BY CENTRAL GOVERNMENT – A STATUS STUDY ON FARMERS OF POLLACHI, COIMBATORE DISTRICT, TAMILNADU

V. Sureshkumar

Assistant Professor, PG & Research Department of Management Science, Sree Saraswathi Thyagaraja College, Pollachi, Coimbatore, Tamilnadu

Cite This Article: V. Sureshkumar, "Impact of Agricultural Schemes by Central Government – A Status Study on Farmers of Pollachi, Coimbatore District, Tamilnadu", *International Journal of Interdisciplinary Research in Arts and Humanities*, Volume 2, Issue 1, Page Number 21-28, 2017

Abstract:

The world's population is predicted to increase to 9 billion people by 2050. Some of the world's highest rates of population growth are predicted to occur in areas that are highly dependent on the agriculture sector (crops, livestock, forestry and fisheries) and have high rates of food insecurity. Growth in the agriculture sector is one of the most effective means of reducing poverty and achieving food security. (FAO)

Key Words: Schemes, Farmers & Cultivation

Introduction:

The word agriculture is the English adaptation of Latin *agricultūra*, from *ager*, "a field", and *cultūra*, "cultivation" in the strict sense of "tillage of the soil" (*Agriculture Dictionary*). Agriculture also called farming or husbandry is the cultivation of animals, plants, fungi, and other life forms for food, fiber, bio-fuel and other products used to sustain life. The history of agriculture dates back thousands of years, and its development has been driven and defined by greatly different climates, cultures, and technologies. 'Agriculture' is now entwined with Food Security, Poverty Eradication and sustainable rural development. Growth in agriculture and in associated rural non-farm employment can have a broad impact in reducing poverty in rural areas, where seven out of ten of the world's poor live IFADⁱ.

Back Ground:

Agriculture began independently in different parts of the globe, and included a diverse range of taxa. At least 11 separate regions of the Old and New World were involved as independent centers of originⁱⁱ. Wild grains were collected and eaten from at least 105,000 years agoⁱⁱⁱ. Rice was domesticated in China between 13,500 and 8,200 years ago, followed by mung, soy and azuki beans. Sheep were domesticated in Mesopotamia between 13,000 and 11,000 years ago^{iv}. From around 11,500 years ago, the eight Neolithic founder crops, emmer and einkorn wheat, hulled barley, peas, lentils, bitter vetch, chick peas and flax were cultivated in the Levant. In the Andes of South America, the potato was domesticated between 10,000 and 7,000 years ago, along with beans, coca, llamas, alpacas, and guinea pigs. Sugarcane and some root vegetables were domesticated in New Guinea around 9,000 years ago. Sorghum was domesticated in the Sahel region of Africa by 7,000 years ago. Cotton was domesticated in Peru by 5,600 years ago^v, and was independently domesticated in Eurasia at an unknown time. In Mesoamerica, wild teosinte was domesticated to maize by 6,000 years ago^{vi}. Civilization was the product of the Agricultural Neolithic Revolution; as H. G. Wells put it, "civilization was the agricultural surplus."^{vii} In the course of history, civilization coincided in space with fertile areas such as The Fertile Crescent, and states formed mainly in circumscribed agricultural lands. The Great Wall of China and the Roman empire's limes (borders) demarcated the same northern frontier of cereal agriculture. This cereal belt fed the civilizations formed in the Axial Age and connected by the Silk Road.

Prospects for Food and Nutrition:

The projections of food demand for the different commodities suggest that the per capita food consumption (kcal/person/ day) will grow significantly. The world average will be approaching 3000 kcal in 2015 and exceeding 3000 kcal by 2030. These changes in the world averages will reflect above all the rising consumption of the developing countries, whose average will have risen from the 2680 kcal in 1997/99 to 2850 kcal in 2015 and close to 3000 kcal in 2030. These gains notwithstanding, there will still be several countries in which per capita food consumption will not increase to levels that would imply significant reductions in the numbers undernourished from the very high levels they have at present. In 2015 there could still be 6 percent of world population (462 million) living in countries with very low levels of food consumption (under 2200 kcal). At the regional level, sub-Saharan Africa would still have in 2015 medium-low levels of per capita food consumption, 2360 kcal/person/day, and even less if Nigeria is excluded from the regional total. These gains in average consumption mean that the great majority of people will be better fed and the incidence of undernourishment should decline. But will it decline sufficiently to achieve the objectives set by the international community? The 1996 WFS set the target that the numbers undernourished (not just the proportion of the population in that condition) should be reduced by half by 2015 at the latest. Improved nutrition, in addition to being a human right and a final objective of development in its own right, is also an essential precondition for societies to make progress towards overall economic and social development within a reasonable time span. This is because undernourished persons are impeded by their very condition

(undernourishment) from fully contributing to, and profiting from, the economic activities that are part and parcel of the development process. Removing the causes of under nutrition is a prime area for public policy interventions (e.g. through public health, sanitation and feeding programmes for pregnant women and children) since economic growth, although a necessary condition, is rarely sufficient by itself to achieve this goal within a reasonable time span.

The implication of the projected higher levels of average national food consumption per person is that the proportion of the population undernourished in the developing countries as a whole could decline from the 17 percent in 1997/99 to 11 percent in 2015 and to 6 percent in 2030. All regions would experience declines in these percentages and, by 2030, all of them, except sub-Saharan Africa, should have incidence in the range of 4 to 6 percent of the population, compared with a range of 9 to 24 percent in 1997/99. Sub-Saharan Africa could still have 15 percent of its population undernourished in 2030, down from 34 percent in 1997/99. (Economic and Social Development Department). Because of population growth, declines in the relative incidence of undernourishment do not necessarily translate into commensurate declines in the absolute numbers (which is of relevance to the WFS target). Notwithstanding the slowdown in their demographic growth, the developing countries' population will still grow from 4555 million in 1997/99 to 5804 million in 2015 and to 6840 million in 2030. Therefore, the numbers undernourished will decline only modestly: from the 776 million in 1997/99 to 610 million in 2015 and to 440 million in 2030. If these projections came true, it would mean that we might have to wait until 2030 before the numbers undernourished are reduced to nearly the target set for 2015 by the WFS, i.e. one half of the 815 million estimated for 1990/92.

Agriculture in India:

Historical Developments:

The history of agriculture in India dates back to industry valley civilization era and even before that in some parts of Southern India. Today India ranks second worldwide in farm output agriculture and allied sectors like forestry and fisheries accounted for 13.7% of the GDP in 2013 about 50% of the workforce. (CIA Fact book). In a longer historical perspective of the last four decades, considerable progress has been made in raising the average world food consumption (measured in kcal/person/day), a variable that is a close correlate of the incidence of undernourishment. The world average kcal/person/day grew by 19 percent since the mid-1960s to 2 800 kcal. What is more important, the gains in the world average reflect predominantly those of the developing countries whose average grew by 31 percent, given that the industrial countries and the transition economies had already reached fairly high levels of per capita consumption in the mid-1960s. This progress in the aggregate of the developing countries has been decisively influenced by the significant gains made by the most populous among them. Of the seven countries with a population of over 100 million (China, Indonesia, Brazil, India, Pakistan, Nigeria and Bangladesh), only Bangladesh remains at very low levels of per capita food consumption. A significant number of countries however failed to participate in this general thrust towards improved national average food consumption levels and, by implication, towards reduced incidence of undernourishment. There are currently still 30 countries with per capita food consumption under 2200 kcal, most of them in sub-Saharan Africa.

Agriculture in India:

Agriculture plays a vital role in India's economy. Over 58 per cent of the rural households depend on agriculture as their principal means of livelihood. Agriculture, along with fisheries and forestry, is one of the largest contributors to the Gross Domestic Product (GDP). As per estimates by the Central Statistics Office (CSO), the share of agriculture and allied sectors (including agriculture, livestock, forestry and fishery) was 15.35 per cent of the Gross Value Added (GVA) during 2015-16 at 2011-12 prices. India is the largest producer, consumer and exporter of spices and spice products. India's fruit production has grown faster than vegetables, making it the second largest fruit producer in the world. India's horticulture output, comprising fruits, vegetables and spices, is estimated to be 283.4 million tonnes (MT) in 2015-16 after the third advanced estimate. It ranks third in farm and agriculture outputs. Agricultural export constitutes 10 per cent of the country's exports and is the fourth-largest exported principal commodity. The agro industry in India is divided into several sub segments such as canned, dairy, processed, frozen food to fisheries, meat, poultry, and food grains.

India is an agriculture based country. It is one of the most important fruit producing nations in the world. Fruit cultivation has been practiced in India since the ancient times, and it has been giving good earning to rural farmers. (Lilly and Dhurga, 2013). India is the world's largest producer of many fresh fruits and vegetables, milk, major spices fresh meat, few crops such as jute, several staples such as millets, castor oil seeds etc. and ranked amongst the world's largest produce items, including many cash crops such as coffee and cotton. India's vast geographical area coupled with varied climate conditions facilities to grow variety of fruits and vegetables. India produced around 81.285 MT fruits and 162.187 MTs of vegetables which accounts for nearly 14% of country's share in the world production of vegetables. (Rais and Sheoran, 2015). The Fruits and Vegetables (F&V) sector has been a driving force in stimulating a healthy growth trend in Indian agriculture. Given the rising share of high value commodities in the total value of agricultural output and their growth potential.(Assocham,2013) it plays a unique role in India's economy by improving the life of people.

Cultivation of these crops is labor incentives and as such they generate lot of employment opportunities for the rural population. (Saurav and Neeraj, 2015).

Table 1: Agricultural Production in India

Year	Food Grain	Oilseeds	Sugarcane	Fruits	Vegetables	Flowers	Total
1996-97	198	23	278	40.5	75.1	0.4	615
1997-98	192	21	280	43.3	72.7	0.4	609
1998-99	204	25	289	44.0	87.5	0.4	649
1999-2000	210	21	299	45.5	90.8	0.5	667
2000-01	197	18	296	43.1	93.8	0.6	649
2001-02	213	21	297	43.0	88.6	0.5	663
2002-03	175	15	287	45.2	84.8	0.7	608
2003-04	213	25	234	45.9	88.3	0.6	607
2004-05	198	24	237	50.9	101.2	0.7	630
2005-06	209	28	281	55.4	111.4	0.7	685
2006-07	217	24	356	59.6	115.0	0.9	773
2007-08	231	30	348	65.6	128.4	0.9	804
2008-09	234	28	285	68.5	129.1	1.0	746
2009-10	218	25	292	71.5	133.7	1.0	742
2010-2011	244	32	342	74.9	146.6	1.0	842
2011-2012	259	30	361	76.4	156.3	1.7	885
2012-2013	257	31	341	81.3	162.2	1.7	874
CAGR (%)	1.63	1.79	1.29	4.46	4.93	10.07	2.22

CAGR = Compound annual growth rate, Source: Ministry of Agriculture, Government of India, and National Horticulture Board.

Recent Trend in Indian Agriculture:

- ✓ At 179.9 million hectares, India holds the second largest agricultural land in the world
- ✓ With 20 agri-climatic regions, all 15 major climates in the world exist in India. The country also possesses 46 of the 60 soil types in the world
- ✓ Total food grains production in India reached an all-time high of 259.3 million tonnes in FY12. Rice and wheat production in the country stood at 105.3 and 94.9 million tonnes, respectively
- ✓ India is the largest producer of pulses, milk, tea, cashew and jute; and the second largest producer of wheat, rice, fruits and vegetables, sugarcane, cotton and oilseeds

Department of Agriculture:

The Department of Agriculture and Cooperation under the Ministry of Agriculture is the nodal organisation responsible for development of the agriculture sector in India. The organisation is responsible for formulation and implementation of national policies and programmes aimed at achieving rapid agricultural growth through optimum utilisation of land, water, soil and plant resources of the country. The DAC is organized into 26 Divisions and has four attached offices and twenty-one subordinate offices which are spread across the country for coordination with state level agencies and implementation of Central Sector Schemes in their respective fields. Further, two Public Sector Undertakings, eight autonomous bodies, ten national level cooperative organizations and one authority are functioning under the administrative control of the Department. Agriculture Census, Agricultural Marketing, Cooperation, Credit, Crops, Drought Management, Extension, Horticulture, Information Technology, Integrated Nutrient Management, Macro Management, Mechanization and Technology, Natural Resources Management, Oilseeds, Plan Coordination, Policy, Plant Protection, Rashtriya Krishi Vikas Yojana, Rainfed Farming System, Seeds, Technology Mission on Oilseeds, Pulses and Maize, KISSAN Call centres, etc.

Agriculture in Tamilnadu:

Tamil Nadu has historically been an agricultural state, while its advances in other fields launched the state into competition with other areas. Agriculture is heavily dependent on the river water and monsoon rains. The perennial rivers are Palar, Cheyyar, Ponnaiyar, Kaveri, Meyar, Bhavani, Amaravati, Vaigai, Chittar and Tamaraparani. Non-perennial rivers include the Vellar, Noyyal, Suruli, Siruvani, Gundar, Vaipar, Valparai and Varshali. Tamil Nadu is also the leading producer of kambu, corn, rye, groundnut, oil seeds and sugarcane in India. At present, Tamil Nadu is India's second biggest producer of rice. Tamil Nadu is the home to Dr. M. S. Swaminathan, known as the "father of the Green Revolution" in India. The town of Namakkal is a major poultry hub of India and Erode is one of the major producers of turmeric in India. (Government Policy Notes)

Major Fruits and Vegetables Grown in Tamilnadu:

The State is the fourth largest producer of horticultural crops in the country. Tamil Nadu produces 22.00 m. MT of horticultural produce from an area of 1.49 m. ha. and accounts for 7.9% of total horticultural

production in the country. The major horticulture produce comprises vegetables (39.5%), fruits (33.6%) and plantation crops (22.0%).

Review of Literature:

- ✓ Deshingkar (2003) expressed that laborers constitute a vital input in agricultural production, but they are migrating to different parts of the country for earning a better livelihood, adding to the existing imbalance between labor demand and supply of laborers.
- ✓ Brahma, Prakash, Srivastava, Sushila.,and Lal S. (1997) studied constraints to Indian agricultural exports, which are lack of suitable varieties and improved technology of production, low production and low exportable surplus, poor quality, high cost of production. Protectional tariff in developed countries, stiff competition in international markets, lack of publicity and R&D support, poor market intelligence, export in the form of raw materials rather than value added product, no brand status to commodities, inadequate infrastructure, poor storage, processing and packaging system, inadequate cargo space and high air freight are the major constraints in boosting the exports of these commodities.
- ✓ Sawant and Diwan (1979) in their study of 150 villages in two taluks of Maharashtra observed a fall in female work participation and decline in self employment opportunities in developed villages.
- ✓ Government of India in its agricultural annual report (2010-11) stated that through new farm practices under NFSM nearly 50 percent of the rice districts (70 out of 143), 33 percent of the wheat districts (41 out of 138) and around 50 percent of pulses districts (74 out of 159) have recorded more than 10 to 20 percent increases in productivity compared to the base year of 2006-07.

Central Government Schemes for Farmers of Pollachi:

1. National Food Security Mission (NFSM): The National Development Council (NDC) in its 53rd meeting held on 29th May, 2007 adopted a resolution to launch a Food Security Mission comprising rice, wheat and pulses to increase the annual production of rice by 10 million tons, wheat by 8 million tons and pulses by 2 million tons by the end of the Eleventh Plan (2011-12). Accordingly, a Centrally Sponsored Scheme, 'National Food Security Mission' (NFSM), was launched in October 2007. The Mission met with an overwhelming success and achieved the targeted additional production of rice, wheat and pulses. The Mission is being continued during 12th Five Year Plan with new targets of additional production of food grains of 25 million tons of food grains comprising of 10 million tons rice, 8 million tons of wheat, 4 million tons of pulses and 3 million tons of coarse cereals by the end of 12th Five Year Plan.

2. National Mission for Sustainable Agriculture: Sustaining agricultural productivity depends on quality and availability of natural resources like soil and water. Agricultural growth can be sustained by promoting conservation and sustainable use of these scarce natural resources through appropriate location specific measures. The focus of NMSA will be to infuse the judicious utilization of resources of commons through community based approach. NMSA will cater to key dimensions of 'Water use efficiency', 'Nutrient Management' and 'Livelihood diversification' through adoption of sustainable development pathway by progressively shifting to environmental friendly technologies, adoption of energy efficient equipments, conservation of natural resources, integrated farming, etc. Besides, NMSA aims at promoting location specific improved agronomic practices through soil health management, enhanced water use efficiency, judicious use of chemicals, crop diversification, progressive adoption of crop-livestock farming systems and integrated approaches like crop-sericulture, agro-forestry, fish farming, etc.

3. National Mission on Oilseeds and Oil Palm (NMOOP):

Mission Targets: National Mission on Oilseeds and Oil Palm (NMOOP) envisages increase in production of vegetable oils sourced from oilseeds, oil palm and TBOs from 7.06 million tonnes (average of 2007-08 to 2011-12) to 9.51 million tonnes by the end of Twelfth Plan (2016-17). The Mission is proposed to be implemented through three Mini Missions with specific target as detailed below:

Mini Mission (MM)	Target of 12th Plan
MM I on Oilseeds	Achieve production of 35.51 million tones and productivity of 1328 kg/ha of oilseeds from the present average production & productivity of 28.93 million tonnes and 1081 kg/ha during the 11th Plan period respectively.
MM II on Oil Palm	Bring additional 1.25 lakh hectare area under oil palm cultivation through area expansion approach in the States including utilization of wastelands with increase in productivity of fresh fruit bunches (FFBs) from 4927 kg per ha to 15000 kg per ha.
MM III on TBOs	Enhance seed collection of TBOs from 9 lakh tonnes to 14 lakh tonnes and to augment elite planting materials for area expansion under waste land.

4. Minimum Support Prices (MSP): Minimum Support Price (MSP) is a form of market intervention by the Government of India to insure agricultural producers against any sharp fall in farm prices. The minimum support prices are announced by the Government of India at the beginning of the sowing season for certain crops on the basis of the recommendations of the Commission for Agricultural Costs and Prices (CACP). MSP is price fixed by Government of India to protect the producer - farmers - against excessive fall in price during

bumper production years. The minimum support prices are a guarantee price for their produce from the Government. The major objectives are to support the farmers from distress sales and to procure food grains for public distribution. In case the market price for the commodity falls below the announced minimum price due to bumper production and glut in the market, government agencies purchase the entire quantity offered by the farmers at the announced minimum price.

5. Mission for Integrated Development of Horticulture: (Subsuming Interventions Under NHM, HMNEH, NBM, NHB, CDB & CIH) Mission for Integrated Development of Horticulture (MIDH) is a Centrally Sponsored Scheme for the holistic growth of the horticulture sector covering fruits, vegetables, root & tuber crops, mushrooms, spices, flowers, aromatic plants, coconut, cashew, cocoa and bamboo. MIDH will have the following sub-schemes and area of operation

S.No	Sub Scheme	Target Group / Area of Operation
1.	NHM	All states & UTs except states in NE and Himalayan Region
2.	HMNEH	All states in NE and Himalayan Region.
3.	NBM	All states & UTs
4.	NHB	All states & UTs focusing on commercial horticulture
5.	CDB	All States and UTs where coconut is grown.
6.	CIH	NE states, focusing on HRD and capacity building.

MIDH will work closely with National Mission on Sustainable Agriculture (NMSA) towards development of Micro-Irrigation for all horticulture crops and protected cultivation on farmers' field. MIDH will also provide technical advice and administrative support to State Governments/ State Horticulture Missions (SHMs) for the Saffron Mission and other horticulture related activities like Vegetable Initiative for Urban Clusters (VIUC), funded by Rashtriya Krishi Vikas Yojana (RKVY)/NMSA

6. National Crop Insurance Programme:

Component-I: Modified National Agricultural Insurance Scheme (MNAIS): Modified National Agricultural Insurance Scheme (MNAIS) aims at supporting sustainable production in agriculture sector, thereby ensuring food security, crop diversification and enhancing growth and competitiveness of agriculture sector besides protecting farmers from production risks.

Crops Coverage:

- ✓ Food crops (Cereals, Millets & Pulses),
- ✓ Oilseeds
- ✓ Annual Commercial / Horticultural crops

7. National Agriculture Development Programme (NADP):

Rashtriya Krishi Vikas Yojana (RKVY): To spur growth in the Agriculture and allied sectors, National Development Council (NDC), in its meeting held on 29th May, 2007 observed that a special Additional Central Assistance (ACA) Scheme be introduced to incentivize States to draw up comprehensive agriculture development plans taking into account agro-climatic conditions, natural resources and technology for ensuring more inclusive and integrated development of agriculture and allied sector.

Research Methodology:

Objectives:

- ✓ To study the central government agricultural schemes.
- ✓ To study the structure of flow of schemes from central to State.
- ✓ To analyze the impact of central schemes on cultivation in Tamilnadu (Pollachi).
- ✓ To identify the problems existing in the field.
- ✓ To evolve suitable remedial measures.

Primary Sources:

Primary data obtained from farmers, agricultural labourers, Agriculture Department Officials, Extension officers and other stakeholders through interview schedules, Direct Interviews, and Focus Group Discussions.

Impact of Central Schemes on Cultivation in Tamilnadu (Pollachi):

- ✓ Most of the farmers are doing inter cropping between the coconut trees and some of the inter crops are banana (Poovan and Monthan) , ground nut, sesamum, tapioca, Green manure crops and fodder crops(Napier grass and guinea grass), elephant foot yam, Cocoa, vanilla, Turmeric, Arecanut, Maize, Sorghum.
- ✓ Young enterprising farmers / rural youths are coming forward to provide custom services to all sections of the farmers, by taking the risk of heavy investment.
- ✓ Farmers are yet to practice the scientific soil and moisture conservation activities especially in dry land areas and heavy seasonal use and keeping idle without use in the rest of the year.
- ✓ Most of the proposed strategies target the big farmers, while the small and marginal farmers are left vulnerable.

- ✓ There exists scope for organizing more number of entrepreneurial development programmes to the rural youths and to the innovative large farmers.
- ✓ Soil and climatic conditions are highly favorable for raising many horticultural crops.
- ✓ The state maintain for horticulture development in the form of National Horticulture Mission is an added strength to grow a variety of horticultural crops.
- ✓ Most of the fruit crops are highly season-bound and hence the year-round production is not possible.
- ✓ A large number of commission mandies, wholesalers and retailers are eking out their livelihood through rendering marketing services to farmers and consumers.

Problems Faced by Farmers in Pollachi:

The following section presents the details of the problems that were highlighted in the Focussed Group Discussions.

Field Related Problems:

- ✓ The farmers are not using the uniform cropping system. There is no proper systematic cropping pattern among the farmers and they are planting the crops as they wish and this will leads to spreading of diseases between the crops.
- ✓ The Focused Group Discussion as well as the field experts view highlighted that paucity of agricultural labor especially for carrying out the weeding and transplanting operations. The fact that there are suitable equipments to meet these specific requirements of the pre and post harvest operations for the farmers. However non availability of the equipment is a major concern that is affecting the productivity of agriculture, more importantly, the small and marginal farmers' do not have the required financial resources to meet the prohibitive cost of these machines.
- ✓ Despite the fact India is a largest producer of Horticulture products and the Coimbatore city being considered as "Horticulture city", the problem of adequate cold storage facilities as actually accentuated the problem of perishability of diverse Horticulture products.
- ✓ A peculiar problem of agriculture supply chain management is the logistics to move out the farm produce to the marketing outlet within the shortest span of time. This calls for improved micro as well as macro transport logistics.
- ✓ In the field of micro crop level management, the study has found that not many farmers regularly test the soil for fertility and adopt suitable remedial measures to augment better variety of crops to be cultivated.
- ✓ The working group constituted by the Ministry of water resources in 1991 estimated that about 2.46 million hectares in irrigated commands suffered from water logging and 3.30 million hectares had been affected by salinity.
- ✓ India being the second largest producers of milk in the world, suffers from inadequate storage and marketing access to small and medium milk producers.
- ✓ The cost and availability of laborers for agriculture have become a major bottleneck and to address this problem as well as to enhance efficiency of the farmers.
- ✓ The high cost and high profit yielding horticultural crops have not penetrated to the small farmers, who were not able to meet the prohibitive cost of cultivating high profit yielding horticulture crops like saffron, and spices like cardamom, sincona, etc
- ✓ Most of the fruit crops are highly season-bound and hence the year-round production is not possible.

Scheme Related Problems:

- ✓ National Mission for Sustainable Agriculture lacks adequate regulatory framework required to meet climate change related challenges to agriculture.
- ✓ Most of the proposed strategies target the big farmers, while the small and marginal farmers are left vulnerable.
- ✓ The government should take some policy measures to reduce the middleman intervention in the market and also to take some initiatives to upgrade the infrastructure of the market yard facilities. The most profitable production areas are Maharashtra, Gujarat and Tamil Nadu.
- ✓ The farmers have reported ineffective monitoring system by the field experts.
- ✓ Crop insurance was relying on yield data and the data was often delayed.
- ✓ The general problem of grains produced by farmers being sold at extremely subsidized prices through the Public Distribution System gained a major focus in the Focussed Group Discussion. The farmers felt the rice being sold at subsidized price is being more used for fowls than human consumption. Many felt it is a grave insult.
- ✓ The Focussed Group Discussion highlighted corruption at the gross root level by the government official who are in the charge of procurement and payment.
- ✓ The farmers reported a low or very little area coverage by many schemes.

Price Related Problems:

- ✓ The problem in the price and supply front is more often 'catch 22' situation. Either the farmer has to face the inevitable loss due to perishability of the products or sell at cut throat prices, either they are damned.
- ✓ Minimum support prices that it declares for various agricultural crops should give the farmers a profit of reasonable profit over their cost of production.
- ✓ Facilitation of Contract Farming between farmers and bulk buyers in the state with financial assistance.
- ✓ All the farmers were aware about Minimum Support Price but none of them knew it before the sowing season.

Market Related Problems:

- ✓ High propensities of indebtedness forces the farmers to sell their produce immediately after harvesting and are very much affected.
- ✓ The farmers' share of consumers rupee is grossly affected by the inter play of various mediators and private players and exploitation of corporate giants.
- ✓ The problems faced by the farmers in respect to marketing pricing of the produce are highly disadvantaged before the unscrupulous marketing intermediaries who profit more from exploitation.
- ✓ The farmers are at the mercy of intermediaries for marketing their produce.

Suggestions:

- ✓ The lack of farm equipments for weeding and transplanting operations can be addressed by the government making available the equipments on a lending basis or provide soft loans with low interest for farmers to buy and use them.
- ✓ The problem of inability to adopt suitable crops according to the climatic conditions can be overcome by educating the farmers on use of drip irrigation facilities and suitable rainwater harvesting and proper watershed management.
- ✓ A central warehousing with adequate cold storage facilities at affordable cost should be built by the central government and provide adequate assistance to the states which are the fore runners of surplus Horticultural products like Tamilnadu. Moreover, the field experts view the fast perishable items like vegetables, fruits to be addressed by strengthening and expanding food processing industry especially the package industry (canned products).
- ✓ The micro level inputs will certainly enable the small farmers to overcome their logistic constraints.
- ✓ The problem of testing of soil fertility can be addressed through a holistic development required for micro crop level management across the state of Tamilnadu. Further, most of the farmers cultivate crops according to their traditions and customs which is more often devoid of marketing demands.
- ✓ The problem of water scarcity can be mitigated only by effective water shed management.
- ✓ The problem of marketing of milk can be effectively handled through agricultural marketing cooperatives in the lines of Amul diary, in Kaira district of Gujarat.
- ✓ The shortage of labour problem can be effectively addressed by adopting collective farming practices. A field expert opined that Mahatma Gandhi National Rural Employment Guarantee Act can be extended by following the Kerala example in Tamilnadu.
- ✓ Considering the value of the Horticulture produce and high export potential, the government should take efforts to subsidize these crops for cultivation by small farmers and their co operations.
- ✓ The problem of perishability can be addressed by developing in house climatic controlled environment for cultivation of crops. The government may assist the growth of the industry through assets creation and capital generation through organizations like NABARD.
- ✓ Formulation of exclusive co operative societies and marketing federations.
- ✓ Focusing on accountability through critical based appraisal system needs to be formulated and implemented.
- ✓ The recent practice of introducing weather based Insurance schemes to be expanded and strengthened.
- ✓ Gradually the subsidized pricing mechanism will have to be replaced by open market pricing system like the industrial products.
- ✓ Corrupt free administration through a tall order is highly emparitive.
- ✓ The schemes should be customized to meet the varying requirements of the farmers.
- ✓ Online marketing facilities which have been introduced in limited areas for some specific products in the country needs to be strengthened in Tamilnadu as well.
- ✓ The policy on support price mechanism should adequately address the reasonable profit margin for the farmers who sell.
- ✓ Public Private Partnership model like of ITC, HUL, Reliance and upcoming Patanjali networks.
- ✓ The timing of the announcement of Minimum Support Price by the government machinery should be proximate to the sowing season. (As felt by majority of farmers in the Focused Group Discussion)
- ✓ The government should widen procurement from one or two products to more quantities.

- ✓ Government should come forward to open more procurement outlets and enhance the Minimum Support Price at market rates.
- ✓ The direct access model for sharing the farm process like vegetable sandais in Tamilnadu (Uzhavar Sandhai) can be followed.
- ✓ The problem of intermediaries can be addressed by the government regulated procurement outlets with sufficient monetary mechanism for better Minimum Support Price.

Conclusion:

This study titled “Impact of agricultural schemes by central government – a status study on farmers of Pollachi, Coimbatore district, Tamilnadu” was conducted in the Pollachi north, south and Anamalai geographical jurisdictions of the Block Development offices in Tamilnadu. This study has found out that Mission of Integrated Development of Horticulture (MIDH or NHM) is most popular among the farmers in Pollachi. The least awareness has been shown in all the blocks in respect to National Crop Insurance Programme. This may be due to the fact that a scheme has not been much highlighted to enhance the awareness among the farmers. This is all the major important due to several places in Tamilnadu facing draught situation and intense crop facilities.

References:

1. Deshingkar, P. and Start, D. (2003). Seasonal Migration for Livelihoods, Coping, Accumulation and Exclusion. Working Paper No. 220, Overseas Development Institute, London.
2. Brahma, Prakash, Srivastava, Sushila, and Lal S. (1997). "Impact of New Policy on Agricultural Commodities for India", Indian Journal of Agricultural Economics, Vol. 50, No.3, July-Sept.
3. Sawant S.D. and Ritu Diwan (1979), “Rural Female labour” Economic and Political Weekly, Vol.XIV, No.30, pp.1091-1099
4. K. Veerakumar (2016) article titled “A Study on Impact of Customer Satisfaction on Brand Loyalty” International Journal of Scientific Research and Modern Education, Vol-I, Issue-I, June – 2016. P.No.661-663.
5. N. Chandrakala & Dr. P. Kanchana Devi, (2016) “A Study On Attitude of the Organic Farmers with Supply Chain Management on the Market for Their Commodities with Special Reference to Coimbatore District” International Journal of Multidisciplinary Research and Modern Education, ISSN (Online): 2454 – 6119, Volume II, Issue II, Page Number 154-159.
6. N. Chandrakala & Dr. P. Kanchana Devi, (2016) “The Study on the Attitude of the Organic Farmers with Special Reference to the Coimbatore District”, International Journal of Applied and Advanced Scientific Research, Volume 1, Issue 1, Page Number 186-191.
7. P. Senthilkumar, “A Study on Investment Pattern and Awareness of Farmers in Pollachi Thaluk”, International Journal of Interdisciplinary Research in Arts and Humanities, Volume 2, Issue 1, Page Number 4-8, 2017.

i. International Fund for Agricultural Development
ii. Larson, G.; Piperno, D. R.; Allaby, R. G.; Purugganan, M. D.; Andersson, L.; Arroyo-Kalin, M.; Barton, L.; Climer Vigueira, C.; Denham, T.; Dobney, K.; Doust, A.N.; Gepts, P.; Gilbert, M. T. P.; Gremillion, K. J.; Lucas, L.; Lukens, L.; Marshall, F. B.; Olsen, K.M.; Pires, J.C.; Richerson, P.J.; Rubio De Casas, R.; Sanjur, O.I.; Thomas, M.G.; Fuller, D.Q. (2014). "Current perspectives and the future of domestication studies". Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences. **111** (17): 6139
iii. Harmon, Katherine (17 December 2009). "Humans feasting on grains for at least 100,000 years". Scientific American. Retrieved 28 August 2016
iv. Ensminger, M.E.; Parker, R.O. (1986). Sheep and Goat Science (Fifth ed.). Interstate Printers and Publishers. ISBN 0-8134-2464-X
v. Broudy, Eric (1979). The Book of Looms: A History of the Handloom from Ancient Times to the Present. UPNE. p. 81. ISBN 978-0-87451-649-4.
vi. S. Johannessen and C. A. Hastorf (eds.) Corn and Culture in the Prehistoric New World, Westview Press, Boulder, Colorado.
vii. H. G. Wells (1914). World Set Free. Macmillan. p. 194.